

Procedures Used in Translating Some Lexical Challenges in the Translated Book "*Revolution and Foreign Policy: The Case of South Yemen (1967-1987)*"

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Article History

Received: 14/10/2025
Accepted: 25/12/2025
Published: 20/1/2026

Abstract

This study explores the lexical challenges that faced the researcher/translator when he translated a historical book entitled "*Revolution and Foreign Policy: The Case of South Yemen (1967-1987)*". In addition, it aimed to detect the translation procedures used by the translator/researcher to deal with these lexical problems. The translator/researcher employed Ghazala's (2008) model to identify lexical problems of translation faced by the translator. It only concentrated on six lexical problems (idioms, metaphors, collocations, similes, proper nouns and polysemy). The study used descriptive qualitative design to find these lexical problems, and detect translation procedures to solve them. The results of the study indicated that there were too many lexical problems discovered in the book, therefore, many translation theorists' procedures were used such as transference, naturalization, literal translation, transposition, functional equivalent, omission, modulation, paraphrase, and many procedures were used to render the figurative language (metaphors and similes). It also examines how Ghazala's model provides systematic procedures to address these challenges. This research contributes to the field of translation studies by providing a practical application of theoretical models and offering recommendations for future translators working with similar texts.

Keywords: Historical book, lexical problems, translation, translation procedures

الملخص

تستقصي هذه الدراسة التحديات المعجمية التي واجهت الباحث/المترجم عندما قام بترجمة كتاب تاريخي من الإنجليزية إلى العربية بعنوان "الثورة والسياسة الخارجية: اليمن الجنوبي من 1967-1987م". وأيضاً هدفت الدراسة إلى اكتشاف أساليب الترجمة (الاستراتيجيات) التي استخدمها الباحث/المترجم من أجل معالجة هذه المشاكل المعجمية. استخدم الباحث نماذج غزالة (2008) في سرد هذه المشاكل. وقد تم التركيز على ست مشاكل معجمية هي: المصطلحات والاستعارات والتلازمات اللفظية والتشبيهات وأسماء الأعلام والألفاظ متعددة المعاني. استخدمت الدراسة المنهج الوصفي النوعي للوصول إلى هذه المشاكل واكتشاف الأساليب المستخدمة من أجل التغلب عليها. أشارت نتائج الدراسة إلى وجود العديد من تلك المشاكل في الكتاب, لذلك تم استخدام أساليب مناسبة استخدمها باحثو الترجمة مثل التعريب اللفظي لأسماء الأعلام والتطبيع/التطويع والترجمة الحرفية والقلب القواعدي والمكافئ الوظيفي والحذف وتقييد المعنى والتحوير, وتم استخدام عدة أساليب في ترجمة اللغة المجازية (الاستعارات والتشبيهات). يساهم هذا البحث في إضافة معرفة إلى حقل دراسات الترجمة من خلال تقديم تطبيق عملي للنماذج النظرية وتقديم توصيات للمترجمين والباحثين في نصوص مشابهة.

الكلمات المفتاحية: كتاب تاريخي, مشاكل الترجمة, الترجمة, أساليب الترجمة

Introduction

Translation is a complex process that aims to convey the meaning of the source text accurately to readers of the target language. Essentially, it involves decoding the meaning and form of the source language and then re-encoding it in the target language. Various scholars have offered definitions for translation. Ghazala (2008, p.1) defines translation as generally referring to "all the processes and methods used to render and/or transfer the meaning of the source language text into the target language as closely, completely and accurately as possible." According to Munday (2008, p. 5) translation "can refer to the product (the text that has been translated) or the process (the act of producing the translation." Newmark (2001) defines it as the attempt to replace a message or statement in one language with an equivalent message or statement in another. Similarly, Catford (1965) defines translation linguistically as the process of "replacement of textual material in one language (SL) by equivalent textual material in another language (TL)." (p. 20). On the other hand Nida (1964, p. 166) and Nida and Taber (1969, p. 12) used the term dynamic equivalence, therefore, translation is defined as "the closest natural equivalent of the source-language message, first in terms of meaning and secondly in terms of style". Therefore, according to this view towards translation in this sense, they indicate that readers of the translated text should get the same effect gotten by readers of the source text. Larson (1984) indicates that a translator can use two main categories of methods: methods that focus on transferring the Source Language to Target Language such as literal translation, and methods that transfer the implied meaning of the SL to the TL such as functional equivalent.

There are many difficulties that emerge throughout the translation process since every language portrays the world in diverse way and has its own syntax variance. To solve that in the actual act of translating, a translator takes a number of measures, bearing in mind the theoretical perspectives and suggestions in this regard. Among such measures are identifying the type of the SL text, the purpose of translation, the type of readership and the strategies involved in the process of rendering.

The translator aims for a wide audience, catering to both educated and lay readers. His/her goal is to convey the source text's content in a clear, natural, and understandable manner. This reader-oriented approach ensures a smooth reading experience, prioritizing the target audience.

After adopting this approach, considering factors like readership, translation purpose, and text type, the researcher/translator began the process of translation. He identified and analyzed specific translation challenges in lexis described in Ghazala's (2008) model. Finally, he addressed these challenges using established translation procedures from Newmark (2001), Vinay & Darbelnet (1995), Baker (2011), Catford (1965), Venuti (1995) ensuring consistency with the overall reader-oriented strategy.

In this study, the researcher presents sample extracts, showing lexical problems encountered through the process of rendering the book, "*Revolution and Foreign Policy: The Case of South Yemen (1967-1987)*", annotating them and discussing how they can be solved by means of consulting procedures supposed to be used as a means of solution for such problems. Moreover, the translator/researcher comments on them by means of presenting some ST extracts that will be selected randomly, with their translations in the TL (Arabic).

Statement of the Problem

During translating the historical book "*Revolution and Foreign Policy: The Case of South Yemen (1967-1987)*" into Arabic, the translator/researcher encountered many translation problems in lexis, grammar, style and culture. The translator/researcher focused on only some lexical problems, by changing them into Arabic using suitable translation procedures used by translation theorists in order to find suitable translations understood by the TL readers. Some of these lexical problems that were encountered in the book were determined to Ghazala's (2008) model: idioms, metaphors, collocations, similes, proper nouns and polysemy, which are considered the most difficult for the translators.

Research Questions

- 1) What were the lexical problems that encountered the translator/researcher when he translated the historical book *Revolution and Foreign Policy: The Case of South Yemen (1967-1987)* from English into Arabic?
- 2) What were the suitable translation procedures used to solve these problems?

Significance of the Study

The significance of this study stems from the importance of the historical book "*Revolution and Foreign Policy: The Case of South Yemen (1967-1987)*" by Fred Halliday. It is informative in nature, reviewing historical facts about South Yemen. Furthermore, this Arabic translation of the book will help researchers concerned in historical annotated translation in presenting the solutions for the lexical problems by using strategies based on various theoretical backgrounds.

Delimitation of the Study

This study is delimited to:

- 1- Discovering the lexical problems during translating the book *Foreign Policy: The Case of South Yemen (1967-1987)* from English into Arabic.
- 2- Identifying only six lexical aspects (idioms, metaphors, collocations, similes, proper nouns and polysemy).
- 3- Finding solutions for these problems by choosing certain procedures from the theoretical background of translation.

The Source Book and its Translation Version

This study tackles and deals with a historical book entitled "*Revolution and Foreign Policy: The Case of South Yemen (1967-1987)*" by Fred Halliday. It is informative in nature, reviewing facts and historical events about the state of South Yemen. The book covers some aspects of the history of South Yemen over the period of 1967-1987, casting light on the nature of foreign policy of such country, reviewing the domestic conflicts over power and the death-defying struggle run by Yemeni people against the British colony to gain their liberation, covering its relations with the West and other countries, including USA, USSR, China, Germany, France, Cuba, and highlighting its conflicts with its neighbors like North Yemen, Saudi Arabia and Oman. It was translated from English into Arabic by the researcher and Nasr Mohammed Ahmed Shaikh in 2024.

Literature Review

Lexical Problems

According to Ghazala (2008, pp. 19-20), lexical problems are centered around the level of word, fixed phrases and expressions above word level. Therefore, he listed the lexical problems to the components of language as follows: "synonymy, polysemy, monosemy, collocations, special fixed phrases (idioms and proverbs), figurative language (metaphors and similes), proper names, titles, geographical terms, (political) institutional terms and UN acronyms." (p.ii). According to Ghazala (2008, p.83) the translation problem stems when many translators sometimes misunderstand the intended meaning of the words and recourse to word for word translation, ignoring the matter of context and combinations in which such words are used. Based on this idea, Ghazala sub-classified lexical problems into word level problems and above word level fixed expressions as follows:

Word level problems

Proper nouns

The problems of translating cultural terms are among the most difficult lexical problems that are discussed. Among such terms are proper nouns, political establishments, geographical terms, acronyms, etc. Ghazala (2008) indicates that translation of proper nouns is not so easy as people think. Therefore, he presented three procedures for translation proper nouns: transcription, transcription/naturalization and naturalization.

1. Transcription/Transliteration/Transference: "It is merely a transcription of the sounds of the foreign term in Arabic letters." (Ghazala, 2021, p. 294). Examples of this procedure:

1. Amanda	أماندا
2. Bill	بيل
3. Bob	بوب
4. Charles	تشارلز
5. Clive	كلايف

2. Transcription/Naturalization: English and Arabic share certain names in religion and history only. Therefore, when these names rendered into Arabic, they are naturalized. For examples:

1. Aaron	هارون
2. Abraham	إبراهيم
3. David	داود
4. Jesus	عيسى
5. John	يحيى/يوحنا

On the other hand, when these names are referred to ordinary people, they are transcribed:

1- Aaron	أرون/إيرون
2- Abraham	إبراهام
3- David	ديفيد
4- Jesus	جيساس
5- John	جون

3. Naturalization: is the adapting of "the SL word first to the normal pronunciation, then to the normal morphology (word-forms) of the TL." (Newmark, 1988, p. 82). Similarly, Ghazala

(2021) indicates that naturalization is the "adaptation of the foreign terms to the grammar, spelling and pronunciation of Arabic Language. Five examples can be cited here:

1. Parliament: برلمان
2. policy: بوليصة
3. physiological: فيسيولوجي
4. bourse: البورصة
5. hallucination: هلوسة

(p.294)

Metaphor

According to *Longman Dictionary of Contemporary English* (app.2009) "Metaphor is a way of describing something by referring to it as something different and suggesting that it has similar qualities to that thing." However, Merriam Webster (app.2021) defines metaphor as "a word or phrase for one thing that is used to refer to another thing in order to show or suggest that they are similar". In the same vein, Ghazala (2008,p.146) stated that metaphor is "an expression of language which is understood in indirect and nonliteral way and used to achieve a kind of resemblance between objects, without stating the similarity in clear terms, or using either articles, 'like 'as", while Newmark (1988, p.104) defined metaphor as "any figurative expression adding that metaphor has two purposes: One is cognitive through which metaphor is used to describe a mental process or state, a concept, a person etc., more comprehensively and concisely than is possible in literal or physical language, while the other is aesthetic which is simultaneous, is to appeal to the senses, to interest, to clarify graphically, to please and surprise". Ghazala (2008, p.146) mentions the components of metaphor as follows.

- a. *Image* (المشبه به): the source of the metaphor. In the example: sunny smile, the source is the sun.
- b. *Object* (المشبه): the idea, thing, or person described (i.e. smile).
- c. *Sense* (وجه الشبه): the direct meaning of the metaphor (i.e. the brilliance of the smile which resembles the brilliance of the shining sun).
- d. *Metaphor* (الاستعارة): the figurative word used in the expression (i.e. sunny).

Simile

Like metaphor, simile is a figurative language in which two entities are compared, as a way of showing similarity between them in some characteristics, by using words such as *like* and *as*. In this regard, Almanna (2016, pp. 112-13) stated that simile is that figurative expression used to describe something by comparing it with something else using comparing markers such as 'like, and as', adding that simile can be classified into three types: *conventional* simile in which the vehicle is an entity representing conventionally certain characteristics to native speakers, *encyclopedic* simile in which proper noun used as a vehicle and *compressed* simile in which information is condensed into a two/ three word lexeme, that is, compound words that include simile like terrorist- type offence.

Polysemy

Polysemy is a word with more than one meaning. Polysemy according to Geeraerts (2010) "refers to the multiplicity of meaning as when a word is used in different fields with different meanings." (p. 12). For example, the word عين has different meanings in Arabic such as عين الصواب and عين الحقيقة both mean "completely right" while on the other hand عين الإبرة means "the needle's eye". Depending on the context, it can also mean a spy. As a result, "they are polysemous because they have the same etymological root and this kind of polysemy might create ambiguity for a translator" (Sadiq 2008, p. 38). So, polysemy has a number of apparently related meanings.

In this sense, the problem is normally posed by polysemy as a translator has confusion when he is required first to determine the exact intended and desired meaning of the SL word that has more than one different meanings, and secondly to elicit and make choice among different meanings of the TL word as a counterpart of the SL's.

Above word level fixed expressions

Collocations

A collocation is the habitual co-occurrence of two or more words in different texts and contexts. According to Crystal (1981, cited in Newmark, 1988, p. 212), a collocation is "a habitual co-occurrence of individual lexical items." To put it more simply, the collocation represents the systematic, habitual, consistent togetherness of two or more words in different texts and contexts. However, Ghazala (2008, p.106) stated that collocation is "a combination of two or more words that always occur together consistently in different texts and contexts in language". Regarding the nature of relation among these collocations, McCawley (1968, p.135) stated that the tendency of words toward certain words is determined by two types of lexical rules: 'strict subcategorization rules and selectional restriction rules'. "The former is predictable, purely semantic in nature, and the violation of it results in ungrammatical combinations. The latter, however, is language specific and less predictable, and its violation might lead to figurative language" (Almanna, 2016, p. 118). In the same vein, Baker (1992, p. 48) stated that the patterns of collocation are largely arbitrary and independent of meaning.

Idioms

Ghazala (2008, p. 128) defines an idiom as "a fixed phrase whose form is usually unchangeable, and whose meaning is always the same, inflexible, metaphorical and indirect." According to *Merriam Webster dictionary* (app. 2021) "idiom is an expression that cannot be understood from the meanings of its separate words but that has a separate meaning of its own", while Baker (2011, p.63) defines an idiom as "a frozen pattern of a language which allows no variation in form and often carries meanings which cannot be deduced from its individual components".

Brinton and Akimoto (1999) presents three criteria that make idioms as a distinguished linguistic phenomenon: semantic transparency, syntactic transformations and degree of substitutability. With respect to the criterion of semantic transparency, idioms are semantically opaque. That is to say, idiom meaning can not be deduced from the sum of the meanings of its parts. Therefore, the meaning of the idiom is called 'unmotivated meaning'. For examples:

- 1- *Kick the bucket.*
- 2- *Hold your horses.*

Here the meaning of *die* cannot be produced from the sum of the meaning of *kick* and *bucket*, and likewise, the meaning of *be patient, slow down* cannot be obtained from *hold, your* and *horses*. As regards the second criterion, Dale et al. (2000) state that an idiom is a rigid word combination to which no generalities apply, nor can it participate in the usual word-order variations. That is, syntactic operations are not allowed. Operations such as passive: (**The bucket was kicked by Sam*); internal modifications: (**Hold your result horses*); and topicalization: (*The bucket Sam kicked*) cannot occur with the idiomatic meaning being retained, Brinton and Akimoto (1999, p.7). According to the criterion of substitutability, the linguistic items in the idioms are unsubstutable. i.e. the elements are fixed, and cannot be reversed or deleted, Brinton and Akimoto (1999). The synonymous lexical items cannot be substituted in the idiom. For example; *crush* and *smash* are synonymous, but, *crush*, cannot be substituted by *smash* in the idiom, *have a crush on*, but not **have a smash on*, Bussmann (1996, p. 216), because any substitution affects the whole meaning of the idiom.

Translation Procedures

Transference/Transliteration

Transference (Newmark, 1988) is named *borrowing* by (Vinay and Darbelnet, 1958). It is a procedure for handling culture-specific terms, which means transferring the SL phonemes into their counterpart phonemes in the TL, focusing on representing the characters or sounds of the source script in the target script rather than translating meaning. In other words, the SL phonemes are transcribed in the TL phonemes. This procedure is based on transferring the phonemes, but not graphemes, of the SL word exactly into the close phonemes in the TL. It became academically important in the 19th century as European scholars sought Roman equivalents for exotic languages like Arabic, Chinese, Greek, Japanese, Persian, Russian, and Sanskrit. For example, the word *Cricket* is transferred into the TL as "كريكت", by transferring its phonemes (phoneme is the smallest unit of speech which can be used to represent a part of word, and which is adaptable according to the position of a letter in a word), but not its graphemes (The written symbols of the word's components), that is, if the word *cricket* is transferred according to its graphemes, it would be "سريسكت" as its graphemes "c, r, i, c, k, e, and t" conventionally represent the components (phonemes) "ت,ك,س,ي,ر,س".

Naturalization

Naturalization is one of the procedures recommended by Newmark (1988), to deal with some culture-specific terms and expressions by means of adapting the SL term to the TL pronunciation, alphabet and grammar by modifying its pronunciation, changing the spelling of its letters into their close counterparts in the TL, and using it in a singular, plural, masculine, feminine, or verb form. (Ghazala, 2008, p. 159). This procedure adapts the source text, makes it read fluently and naturally in the target language, by reducing the effect of foreignness to comply with the target language norms. This procedure is called by Nida (1964) as *functional equivalence*. He emphasized that translation should focus on the target reader's response over literal accuracy, by making adaptations that make the target text sound natural and familiar in the target culture. One of the seven translation procedures by Vinay and Darbelnt (1958) is adaptation, which they indicate that it is a form of naturalization, where naturalness in the target text can be fulfilled by replacing the cultural elements of the source text by

those of the source text culture. For example, the term "bureaucracy" is naturalized into Arabic as "بيروقراطية". Here the word *bureaucracy* is naturalized into the TL pronunciation, alphabet and grammar by means of changing its pronunciation partly through modifying the letter "c" in the syllable "cy" in the SL into "ط" letter in the TL and adding the letter "ة" which represents the sign of feminine in the TL grammar.

Functional equivalent

The idea of this procedure is to look for the equivalent in the TL, which is used exactly in the same context, to give a meaning perfectly identical to that of the SL equivalent. It requires the use of a culture-neutral word (Newmark, 1988). In this procedure, the English cultural term could have exactly and literally the same correspondent term in Arabic (Ghazala, 2008, p. 196). For example: The noun phrase *the Arab league* and its TL equivalent "جامعة الدول العربية" have the same nature in the sense that the TL equivalent "جامعة الدول العربية" performs the identical function of the SL culture-specific term *the Arab league* in the TL and vice versa. To make the point clearer, functional equivalents (of the SL and the TL) are normally linguistically different, while functionally are the same. That is, there is normally no relationship between the form and the literal meaning of the SL cultural, specific term and those of the TL term. However, they share the same function and are used in the same context. The previous SL phrase *Arab league*, literally means "الاتحاد العربي" and its TL equivalent "جامعة الدول العربية" literally means "university of Arab countries". They are linguistically different, but they are culturally the same in terms of function and context.

Transposition

Transposition (also called 'shift' by Newmark, 1988) is a grammatical procedure that involves a change of the grammatical class of words from, say, a verb to a noun, a noun to a verb, an adjective to a verb, and so on. It also involves grammatical structures into different structures in the other language, such as changing singular into plural, a phrase into a clause, or vice versa, a verb phrase into a verb, or vice versa, a noun phrase / a collocation into a single noun, and vice versa, etc. Almanna (2016) indicates that the most important feature of transposition is that it does not change the meaning of the source text. Many English terms have been translated into different grammatical terms in Arabic that are more convenient than those of the original. In all cases, meaning should remain untouched. Here are some examples:

- (1) blameless لا يلام/لا لوم عليه (adjective → noun/verb phrase)
- (2) wrong جانب الصواب (adjective → verb phrase)
- (3) paralexia حَطَل القراءة (noun → noun phrase)
- (4) unanimous بالإجماع (adj. → prepositional phrase) (Ghazala, 2021, p.297).

Vinay and Darbelnet (1995, p. 89) classifies transposition into: obligatory transposition and optional transposition. In the obligatory transposition the translator is obliged or constrained to use a decision to achieve an equivalent in the target language TL. In other words, when in a particular context transposition is necessary to achieve an equivalent meaning in the TT. For example: He merely nodded. The English verb *nodded* is changed to

- 2- Christmas عيد الميلاد instead of (عيد ميلاد المسيح)
 3- Computer الحاسوب instead of (الحاسب الآلي)

According to Ghazala indicates that this procedure is limited in use and it is possible only when the SL term become popular in use. It can be so on in two conditions: "(1) its frequent use in the TL; and (2) its use in full form for some time, may be years." (Gazala, 2008, pp. 207-8).

Procedures of Translating Metaphor and Simile

Metaphor and simile are considered from the most difficult linguistic expressions, and they make actual problems for translators. Traditionally, metaphor is defined as a word or an expression which has departed from its basic meaning to refer to other things. In metaphor, there are two levels of meaning: "surface meaning and deep meaning." (Almanna, 2016, p. 110). Ghazala (2008) presented a clear definition for metaphor "A metaphor is an expression of language which is meant to be used and understood in an indirect, non-literal way. It is a figure of speech that aims at achieving a kind of resemblance between two objects, without stating the similarity in clear terms, or using either article, 'like' or 'as'." (p. 146). Metaphor has four components: "image, object, sense and metaphor" (Ghazala, 2008, p. 146). They can be clarified in the example: *sunny smile*. *Sun* is the source of the metaphor (image), *smile* is the element described (object), the brilliance of the *smile* resembles the brilliance of the shining *sun* (sense), and *sunny* the figurative word used in the expression (metaphor). It is well known that metaphor is the process of utilizing our sociocultural experiences as a way of creating a kind of correspondence between two entities by means of exploiting the **basic (surface) meaning** of language in a form of comparison. However, this is not always true.

Metaphor can sometimes be nonstructural. That is, it does not rely on the surface meaning, nor it takes the form of comparison between entities, but it relies on the **underlying meaning** of language, that is not identical to its surface meaning, to describe a particular entity instead. And this is what constitutes a real challenge for a translator to go deep behind the underlying meaning of metaphor and try to comprehend its intended meaning. For example, the deep underlying meaning of the metaphor "to carry the cane" is "to take the blame for something." As can be seen, its lexical items depart from their basic, straightforward, referential meaning to refer to something else (Almanna, 2016, p. 111).

Similarly, simile can be treated in much the same way as metaphor, however, with using the language of similarity like the words, "like" and "as". Almanna (2016) classifies simile into three types: "*conventional* simile in which the vehicle is an entity representing conventionally certain characteristics to native speakers, *encyclopedic* simile in which proper noun used as a vehicle, and *compressed* simile in which information is condensed into a two/ three word lexeme, that is, compound words that include simile like terrorist- type offence." (pp. 112-13).

In this regard, models of procedures were suggested to deal with such an issue. Among the most public and distinct ones is Newmark's (2001, pp. 88-91) model which includes seven procedures ordered according to preference as follows:

Reproducing the same image in the TL: This procedure is common for translating one-ward metaphor in which the translator attempts to reproduce the same image of the SL in the TL when this metaphorical image is not available before in the TL. For example: The *language* of revolutionary

armed struggle was the main language through which our people addressed the colonial invaders. The image *language* in English is reproduced in Arabic, that is لغة as follows:

كانت لغة الكفاح المسلح الثوري هي اللغة الرئيسية التي من خلالها خاطب شعبنا الاستعمار الغازي.

Replacing the image in the SL with a standard TL: In this procedure, the appropriate cultural equivalent in the TT replaces the ST metaphor. This procedure produces a good process when the image in the source culture has a different understanding in the target culture. For example: *Ray* of hope. Here direct translation of the phrase into شعاع أمل does not work in Arabic. In this case it is preferable in Arabic to use a standard TL word instead of the direct word شعاع, which are in Arabic (برق/بصيص/بارقة أمل) (Ghazala, 2008, p. 150).

Translation of metaphor by simile: According to this procedure the translated metaphor is provided by simile as an attempt to fill the gaps between ST and TT metaphors. For example, the metaphor, "Ali is a fox in astuteness", can be translated into simile as:

علي كالثعلب في الدهاء.

Translation of metaphor (simile) by simile plus sense: In this procedure, the unclear metaphors (simile) can be supported with more explanations so as to be more understood for the TL reader. Furthermore, this procedure can be used to clarify the metaphor and give it more aesthetic value. For example: The issue of Yemeni unity, more generally like that of Arabic unity, can be translated into Arabic as:

إن قضية الوحدة اليمنية, بشكل عام مثلها مثل الوحدة العربية, من ناحية التأثير السلبي, كانت سببا لخلاف كبير بين الدولتين اليمينيتين. In this example the resemblance is between the Yemeni unity and Arab unity, that is, the Yemeni unit is like the Arab unity. In the ST, the resemblance is not stated clearly, so the phrase in Arabic من ناحية التأثير السلبي is added to clarify the simile, and to be understood for the TL reader.

Conversion of metaphor to sense: This procedure is used when the metaphor is useless in the target language and has not that value of the source one. So, the translator can then translate it into sense in the TL. For example: PLO forces were *not* stationed on PDRY-controlled islands at the **mouth** of the red sea. The English metaphor at the *mouth* of the Red Sea is to be rendered into sense in Arabic مدخل البحر الأحمر, which is understood by the TL readers.

Deletion: According to this procedure, the metaphor or simile can be omitted in TL, as they are considered as impractical in the ST, that is, they do not impact on the intended meaning of the ST. For example: The free Yemenis had been allowed to operate in Aden, in part, because British authorities saw them *as* a useful counterweight to Imam in the North. This sentence is rendered into Arabic as:

سُمح لليمنيين الأحرار بالعمل في عدن، من ناحية، لأن السلطات البريطانية اعتبرتهم ثقلا مواز للإمام في الشمال.

Here the resemblance article 'as' was deleted in the TT; it did not affect on the meaning of the ST, since it is still understood for the TL reader.

Same metaphor combined with sense: Beside translating the ST metaphor into the TL, it can be provided with explanation so as to make its meaning clearer and to make sure that the metaphor is understood to the TL reader. For example: You are the water of my life. It can be translated as:

أنت ماء حياتي, ولا أستطيع العيش بدونك.

Method

Nunan (2000, p.23) defines research as a "systematic process of formulating question, collecting relevant data relating to questions, analyzing, interpreting the data and making the results publicly accessible." Here method is a way to examine a problem in a certain issue in order to reach its results; the problem is also labeled a research problem. This section presents the methods used by the researcher to collect data in order to answer the research questions, presenting why the researcher chose the certain research design, and selecting the research sample, and how it is analyzed.

Research design

The descriptive qualitative design was used in this research, through analyzing the content of a number of sentences in the annotated historical book "*Revolution and Foreign Policy: The Case of South Yemen (1967-1987)*" in order to discover the six lexical problems and the translation procedures used by the translator. According to Richards and Schmidt (2010, 475) qualitative research "uses procedures that make use of non-numerical data, such as interviews, case studies, or participant observation." (p.475). According to Creswell (2007), qualitative research is carried out when a researcher would like to search for concise and detailed information that cannot be found by quantitative research. Hence, the technique of observation is used in this study; that is, observation of some sentences from the translated book that contain the defined six lexical problems.

Research data

The data of the present study is both the source English historical book and its translation version. Sixty five samples were chosen randomly from the target Arabic text as follows: proper nouns (32), metaphors (4), similes (3), polysemy (5), collocations (17), and idioms (4).

Procedures of data collection

Sandelowski and Barroso (2007) denote that data collection in a qualitative research may include observations of targeted events, focus group interviews and the examination of documents and artifacts. The data collection procedure involved was carried out as follows:

- 1- The original text was carefully read. The six lexical problems samples were chosen randomly, and compared with their Arabic translations.
- 2- Finding the translation procedures used by the translator/researcher.

Data analysis

The data in this study was analyzed by using the content analysis method. Tavakoli (2012) defines the content analysis method as:

A procedure which is used to convert written or spoken information into data that can be analyzed and interpreted. Content analysis is a qualitative research technique which is used to

quantify aspects of written or spoken text or of some form of visual representation. It is used for analyzing and tabulating the frequency of occurrence of themes, emotions topics, ideas, opinions and other aspects of the content of written and spoken communication. (p.101).

According to this definition, the translator/researcher collected the data collected from both the source book and the translated version was analyzed carefully and connected to the scholars' theories related to the translation procedures and finding the procedures much used by the translator.

Results and Discussion

Proper Nouns

Table 1

No.	English Nouns	Arabic Translation	Translation procedure
1	Abyan	أبين	Transference
2	Radfan	ردفان	~
3	Bab al- Mandeb	باب المنذب	~
4	London	لندن	~
5	Shackleton	شاكلتون	~
6	David Owen	ديفيد أوين	~
7	Syria	سوريا	~
8	Fidel Castro	فيدل كاسترو	~
9	William Casey	وليم كاسي	~
10	Kahtan al-Asha'abi	قحطان الشعبي	Naturalization
11	Ali Nasir Muhammad	علي ناصر محمد	~
12	Sultanate of Aulaqi	سلطنة العوالق	~
13	Sultanate of Audhalia	سلطنة العوائل	~
14	Aden	عدن	~
15	Yaf'a	يافع	~
16	Dhalih	الضالع	~
17	Tripoli	طرابلس	~
18	Tahir	طاهر	~
19	Salih Muslih	صالح مصلح	~
20	Alegria	الجزائر	~
21	Baghdad	بغداد	~
22	Cairo	القاهرة	~
23	Dhofar	ظفار	~
24	Socatra	سقطرى	~
25	Salim Rubiyya Ali	سالم ربيع علي	Transference + Naturalization
26	West Germany	ألمانيا الغربية	Naturalization + Translation
27	Arabian Gulf	الخليج العربي	Translation + Naturalization
28	Persian Gulf	الخليج الفارسي	~

29	Arab sea	البحر العربي	~
30	North Korea	كوريا الشمالية	Transference + Translation
31	Red Sea	البحر الأحمر	Translation
32	Egypt	مصر	~

Starting with *transference* (Newmark, 1988) and *borrowing* (Vinay and Darbelnet, 1958), it is a procedure for handling culture-specific terms, which means transferring the SL phonemes into their counterpart phonemes in the TL, focusing on representing the characters or sounds of the source script in the target script rather than translating meaning. In other words, the SL phonemes are transcribed in the TL phonemes. As regards the source text of study, there is a variety of nouns, whether of people, places, or things, to which the transcription procedure was applied and its consultation achieved a great success. As can be seen in the table above, there are some names written in the SL which were transcribed, but not transliterated as transliteration represents only the grapheme of the phoneme, whilst transcription does represent the phoneme itself, such nouns are transcribed by their counterparts in the TL. The nouns *Salem* and *David*, for instance, were transcribed phoneme by phoneme to their counterpart phonemes in the TL. That is to say, the noun *Salem* was transcribed into its counterpart phonemes as "س، ا، ل، م"، also the noun "David" was transcribed into "د، ي، ف، د" phonemes in the TL. However, there are some phonemes in some nouns that do not correspond with their graphemes in terms of pronunciation, so then do not correspond with their counterparts in the TL. That is to say, some phonemes have more than one realization when rendering from one language into another. In such a case, when one phoneme has a sound variation, these variations are called allophones. For example, the phoneme /g/ is pronounced as "ج" in nouns such *Algeria* (الجزائر), and as "غ" in nouns such as *Baghdad* (بغداد). Taking such an issue into account, such phonemes may pose a problem for translators so as to state the kind of allophone. In this regard, transcription does not make sense, whereas it is limited only to transfer the SL phonemes exactly as they are pronounced into their counterparts in the TL without any change in their qualities. Therefore, the scholars of translation had suggested another procedure called *naturalization* (Newmark, 1988; Nida, 1964), that is, transferring the SL term to the TL pronunciation and grammar (morphemes like suffixes and prefixes) by modifying its pronunciation whether partly or changing one or more of its phonemes so as to be in harmony and closer to the TL ones. The phonemes /s/ and /æ/, as instance, have more than one realization. In nouns such *Syria*, *Scottra* and *Salim*, the /s/ phoneme is transcribed, as it is in the SL, into its counterpart in the TL "س", however in nouns such as *Salih* and *Nasir*, /s/ phoneme is naturalized differently as "ص" phoneme in the TL. Similarly, the phoneme /æ/ in nouns such as *Ahmed* and *Saleh* is transcribed as "ا" in the TL, however, the same phoneme is realized and naturalized phonetically different as "ع" in nouns such as *Abd al Aziz* and *Ali*. Similarly, the phoneme /t/ is transcribed as "ت" in nouns such as *Turki*, however, naturalized as "ط" in nouns such as *Tripoli* "طرابلس" and *Tahir* "طاهر".

Some compound nouns such as *Salim Rubiyya Ali* can be translated into the TL by using two procedures together. In this example the noun *Salim* was transcribed into "سالم", while the nouns *Rubiyya Ali* were naturalized into "رُبَيْع" and "عَلِي", respectively.

Phrases like *Arabian Gulf*, *Persian Gulf* and *Arab sea*, were rendered into Arabic by using the compound procedure Translation + Naturalization, since the second word of each phrase was translated

literally as "الخليج" and "بحر", while the first words were naturalized into "العربي", "الفارسي", and "العرب", respectively, whereas from a grammatical point of view, there are some nouns like *North Korea* and *West Germany* that had been adopted morphologically according to TL grammar. As translation is from English (SL) into Arabic (TL), transferring such nouns, namely *North Korea* and *West Germany*, may pose a problem as they cannot be feminized in the ST while they can be in the TL. Therefore, the adjectival nouns *North* and *West*, attributed to the nouns *Korea* and *Germany* were naturalized by adding the morpheme of feminization "ة" which is a feature only of the TL grammar, but not of the ST. Consequently, the adjectives *North* and *West* will be "شمالية" and "غربية".

Such procedures, namely transcription, naturalization, seem, however, senseless and practically of no importance in dealing with nouns such as *Red Sea* and *Egypt*, so then, to render such nouns, the literal translation was employed, as it can make sense and render the meaning more effectively. Hence, they were translated literally to "البحر الأحمر" and "مصر", respectively. The nouns mentioned above were quoted from the source text of this study.

Metaphor

Table 2

No.	English Metaphorical Expressions	Arabic Equivalences	Procedure used
1	The Fourth Congress of the National Front called for a series of economic measures. (p.21)	دعا المؤتمر الرابع للجبهة القومية إلى اتخاذ سلسلة من التدابير الاقتصادية.	Reproducing the same image in the TT
2	PLO forces were <i>not</i> stationed on PDRY-controlled islands at the mouth of the red sea. (p.44).	لم توجد قوات منظمة التحرير الفلسطينية في الجزر الواقعة على مدخل البحر الأحمر التابعة لـ ج.ي.د.ش.	Converting metaphor into sense
3	The language of revolutionary armed struggle was the main language through which our people addressed the colonial invaders. (p.69)	كانت لغة الكفاح المسلح الثوري هي اللغة الرئيسة التي من خلالها خاطب شعبنا الاستعمار الغازي.	Reproducing the same image in the TT
4	The Yemeni masses in the south struggled with the Yemeni masses in the North shoulder to shoulder in order to bring down the Imam's regime. (p.102).	كافحت الجماهير اليمنية في الجنوب مع الجماهير اليمنية في الشمال جنباً إلى جنب من أجل إسقاط نظام الإمام.	Converting metaphor into sense

The first example "The Fourth Congress of the National Front called for a **series** of economic measures." was translated into "دعا المؤتمر الرابع للجبهة القومية إلى اتخاذ سلسلة من التدابير الاقتصادية". An attempt was made to reproduce the same image in the TL. While translating, the attention was paid to the nature of the ST metaphor and its acceptability to the TT readership. In this regard, the ST metaphor, which literally means several, a set or a group of something of a similar type, is compared or likened to a chain lit. "سلسلة" which is metal rings that are joined together in a line. In this context, such a metaphor is used as a way of achieving a kind of resemblance in terms of the sequence of events and measures. In this regard, it is worth noting that such an SL metaphor neither contradicts with the TLC nor with its readership's background, whereas the *Arabic Modern Dictionary* proves that the word "سلسلة" is derived from the verb "سلسل" which literally means concatenating events, actions etc. in sequence. Consequently, like SL culture, the word "سلسلة" is metaphorically used in the TL culture to mean that events actions etc. happen one after the other in sequence. In this sense, the translator succeeded to be insider in both cultures (SLC, TLC), as he could transfer the same image of the ST metaphor with its form and as well its meaning in the TL.

The second example is "PLO forces were *not* stationed on PDRY-controlled islands at the **mouth** of the red sea." It literally means "فم البحر الأحمر". However, it metaphorically means that part of the sea where it joins another sea (cf. *Longman Dictionary of Contemporary English*, 2009). It is worth noting that there are so many words in the SL that are normally used out of their literal meaning to mean something else. The word *mouth* in the context above, as an instance, literally means that part of the face that is used for eating and producing sounds. However, an attempt was made in the ST to liken that part of the sea where it joins with another sea to that part (mouth) of the face that belongs only to living things, so as to state the beginning or starting point of that sea. Concerning culture, such an expression is normally and effectively used in the Source Language Culture, yet it is not effective enough to produce a close effect in the Target Language Culture, where transferring it literally into the TL does lead to distorting the intended meaning of the ST and does mislead the TT readership. Therefore, the translator replaced the ST image with one that is much more effectively convenient in the TL to make sense and guarantee producing an effect on the TT reader like that produced on the ST's. Hence, he replaced the ST image implicit in the word *mouth* with a standard TL image which is accurately recognized in the word "مدخل". Thus, "مدخل البحر الأحمر".

The third example "The **language** of revolutionary armed struggle was the main language through which our people addressed the colonial invaders", was translated to "كانت لغة الكفاح المسلح الثوري هي اللغة". In such a context, the metaphor is implicit in the phrase "the language of the revolutionary armed struggle", whereby "the struggle" "الكفاح" is talked of in terms of having language which is axiomatically and naturally an attribute of living things. Such an image is created in a single word *language* "لغة", hence an attempt is made to reflect such an image in the TT. Therefore, the translator opted for reproducing the same image in the TT (Newmark, 2001, pp. 88-91), as reproducing it does not negatively affect the intended meaning of the ST message or mislead the TT reader but, on the contrary, retaining it (image) in the TT will show how the TL is so flexible and how its aesthetic aspects are, as well as will guarantee attracting and enjoying the TT readers as opposed to ordinary language that is to a considerable extent dull. In such a context, the translator succeeded in

keeping the same image in the TL as well as in leaving a close effect on the TT reader to that produced on the ST's.

Regarding the fourth example, "The Yemeni masses in the south struggled with Yemeni masses in the North **shoulder to shoulder**", literally means *كافحت الجماهير اليمنية في الجنوب مع الجماهير اليمنية في الشمال* "كفنا إلى كتف". As the metaphor in this context means that the nation in the south Yemen solidified with the nation in the North and fought side by side against the regime of Imam, the acceptability of literal translation for this metaphor is accessible, as it can make sense and the idea of intended meaning of the ST can to some extent be gotten by the TT readers. The translator, however, in an attempt to maintain the naturalness of the context in the TT and to guarantee more acceptability to the TT readership, avoided literal translation and opted for converting metaphor into sense (Newmark, 2001, pp. 88-91). Therefore, in rendering the metaphorical expression *shoulder to shoulder*, apart from its form, an attempt was made to retain its flavor and expressivity in the TT. So, the translator converted the metaphor *shoulder to shoulder* to *جنباً إلى جنب* lit. "side by side".

Simile

Table 3

No.	English similes	Arabic equivalence	Procedures used
1	The issue of Yemeni unity, like that of Arabic unity more generally, has been a cause of considerable friction between the two Yemeni states. (p.99).	فقد كانت قضية الوحدة اليمنية، بشكل عام مثلها مثل الوحدة العربية، من ناحية التأثير السلبي، سبباً لخلاف كبير بين الدولتين اليمنيتين.	Translating simile by simile plus sense
2	The free Yemenis had been allowed to operate in Aden, in part, because British authorities saw them as a useful counterweight to Imam in the North. (p.101).	سُمح لليمنيين الأحرار بالعمل في عدن، من ناحية، لأن السلطات البريطانية اعتبرتهم ثقلاً موازاً للإمام في الشمال.	Omission
3	Aden served as a center for political and propaganda work directed at the outside world. (p.145).	عملت عدن كمركز للعمل السياسي والدعائي الموجه للعالم الخارجي مفيد لجمع المعلومات.	Literal translation

The example "the issue of Yemeni unity, more generally like that of Arabic unity", is translated to "أن قضية الوحدة اليمنية بشكل عام مثلها مثل الوحدة العربية، من ناحية التأثير السلبي". As can be seen, the simile is expressed in the sentence "Yemeni unity is like Arabic unity", in which the entity described by simile is *Yemeni unity*, and the entity to which it is compared to is *Arabic unity*. In this context, the comparison is held between the two entities on the base that the issue of Yemeni unity was a cause of friction between the two Yemeni countries as a result of disagreement on how this unity is to be achieved where each part

tried to exploit the commitment to this unity to interfere in the internal affairs of the other. So, the point of similarity is implicit in that Yemeni unity and Arabic unity share the same conditions regarding achieving them and exploiting the commitment to them. So as to reflect a close effect on the readers of the TT, an attempt has been made to offer some more enlightenment to the translated simile, as the point of similarity is to some extent unclear and ambiguous in the ST, so the translator was required to give more explanation for it in the TT so as to be more clear and understood to the TT reader. In this regard, he added the phrase "من ناحية التأثير السلبي" lit. "in terms of negative effect" and used the noun phrase "مثلها" مثل as an equivalent to the preposition "like" in the ST. This is in agreement with Newmark's procedure (translating simile by simile plus sense) (2001, pp. 88-92)

Another interesting example is "the free Yemenis had been allowed to operate in Aden, in part, because British authorities saw them **as useful counter weight** to Imam in the North". It was translated to "سُمح لليمنيين الأحرار بالعمل في عدن، من ناحية، لأن السلطات البريطانية اعتبرتهم ثقلاً موازاً للإمام في الشمال". As can be seen, the topic (the entity described) is "free Yemenis" and the image (the entity to which the topic is compared) is "Imam" and the common ground of similarity is "counter weight" which is normally used to show the counter balance in power or in influence or any other aspects between two or more opponent powers. As has been shown in the example above, the translator deleted the marker of simile altogether as it is implicitly expressed in the lexical item "اعتبر" lit. "considered". The main reason for such an omission is that the comparison marker "like" is of no importance to the development of the context and omitting it does not harm the author's intentions or alter the context type focus as its sense is kept in another place in the context.

One more example is "Aden served **as** a useful information gathering **post**", which was translated to "عملت عدن كمركز مفيداً لجمع المعلومات". Concerning simile's components, Aden represents the topic of the simile while "the post" represents the vehicle and "gathering information" is considered as the ground of similarity. Regardless of language servitude, in rendering the above example, the translator transferred the components of the ST literally. In such a context, the literal translation was used, as it can make sense and does not change the meaning of the ST message.

Polysemy

Table 4

No.	English polysemous word 'run'	Arabic Equivalents
1	The longer- run direction of South Yemen's foreign policy must, therefore, await the passage of more years. (p.7).	يجب أن ينتظر اتجاه السياسة الخارجية لليمن الجنوبي على المدى الطويل مرور مزيد من السنوات.
2	BP owned the refinery till 1977, and continued to run it under a service contract thereafter." (p.69).	امتلكت شركة بريتش بتروليوم المصفاة حتى عام 1977م. واستمرت في إدارتها بعد ذلك بموجب عقد عمل.
3	Trade between the two countries was considerable, with South Yemen's imports running at an annual average of YD 2.0 million in the years 1969-77. (p.76)	كانت التجارة بين البلدين كبيرة، حيث بلغ متوسط واردات اليمن الجنوبي 2 مليون سنوياً بين عامي 1969-77م.
4	A set of three defensive lines was then constructed on	تم بناء مجموعة من ثلاثة خطوط

	an axis running from the desert to the sea. (p.145)	دفاعية على محور يمتد من الصحراء إلى البحر.
5	The PDRY government willing to risk the survival of its own state by becoming involved in an outright war with Oman that would have run the risk of bringing in other states to support the Sultanate. (p.155).	كانت حكومة جمهورية اليمن الديمقراطية الشعبية على استعداد للمخاطرة ببقاء دولتها من خلال المشاركة في حرب مفتوحة مع عمان, مما كان سيشكل خطرا لجذب دول أخرى لدعم السلطنة.

As can be seen, the word *run* and its derivative *running* in the extracts in table 4 quoted from the source text, are polysemous words with more than one meaning, whose Arabic equivalents here are **مدى**, **إدارة**, **بلغ**, **يمتد**, **سيشكل**. In rendering the word *run* into the TL, the translator took into account the context in which it is used and found that rendering it literally with its common meaning will result in awkward translation, therefore, he thought very carefully about all the possible secondary meanings of it and found that the most convenient ones among such secondary meanings, regarding context, are the meanings: *extent*, *manage*, *amount to*, *extend*, and *make*, respectively. In this way, the translator succeeded in getting the right meanings on the basis of the context. In the examples 1 and 2, the procedure used was transposition (Vinay and Darbelent, 1995, p. 89), since the verb *run* was rendered in Arabic into the nouns **مدى** and **إدارة**.

With respect to the fifth example, omission procedure was applied. The verb *run* was not necessary to be translated to Arabic, and it did not affect on the meaning of the TT, since the translated Arabic verb phrase **سيشكل خطر** is equivalent to the English verb phrase *would have the risk*, without the verb *run*.

Collocations

Table 5

No.	English collocations	Arabic equivalences
1	Civil war (p.9).	حرب أهلية
2	Tribesmen (p.18).	رجال القبائل
3	Oil fields (p.21).	حقول نفطية
4	With deeds and not words (p.22).	بالأفعال لا بالأقوال
6	Inch by inch (p.22).	خطوة بخطوة
7	Net amount (p.66).	المبلغ الصافي
8	Consumer goods (p.37).	سلع استهلاكية
9	Internal affairs (p.66).	الشؤون الداخلية
10	Press conference (p.18)	مؤتمر صحفي
11	Military forces (p.90).	القوات المسلحة
12	Loss of life (p.43).	خسائر في الأرواح
13	Insurance companies (p.23).	شركات تأمين
14	In peace (p.15).	في سلام
15	Trades union (p.70)	نقابة العمال

16	Fund-raising (p.70)	حملة تبرعات
17	Air support (p.17)	دعم جوي

As a way of shortening the distance between the ST and the TT and having a strong relationship between them, an attempt was made to maintain the intended meaning of the ST and its accuracy, however, without affecting the readability and acceptability of the TT.

In doing so, the strategy of literal translation has been adopted so as to maintain the flavor of the ST, and at the same time to produce a readable, fluent and accepted TT. Therefore, in translating the following collocations *civil war* and *net amount*, the translator rendered them literally to "حرب أهلية" and "مبلغ صافي", respectively, as long as doing so would not affect the fluency of the TT. And what is more, their forms and semantic meaning became an integral part of the TT.

Other good examples are *oil fields* and *consumer goods*. They are translated into "حقول نفطية" and "سلع استهلاكية". As can be seen, while translating the preceding examples, the translator opted for transposition (Vinay and Darbelent, 1958/1995, p. 89). In this regard, the translator, for aesthetic and rhetorical reasons, optionally resorted to changing the noun *oil* lit. "نفط" in the ST, with possibility of literal translation, that is "حقول نفط", into the adjective "نفطية", in the TT, which has no equivalent in the SL. Also the noun *consumer* lit. "مستهلك" has been changed to the adjective "استهلاكية".

One more example is the collocational expressions *with deeds not words* and *inch by inch*. The literal translation of them is "بالأفعال لا بالكلمات" and "بوصةً ببوصة". As given above, translating such collocations literally will surely distort the intended goal and meaning of these collocations and does not reflect them more effectively. Thus, to get the more close effective meaning of such collocations in the TT, the translator had to a considerable extent depended on the context of the original in which these collocations were used, whereas the context talks about revolution and inciting nation to stand side by side against reactionary forces to defend their lands and private properties, whereby the translator rephrased the ST collocations. Therefore, the translator, as an attempt to maintain the naturalness and acceptability of the TT, opted for rephrasing the collocations *with deeds not words* and *inch by inch* as "بالأفعال لا بالأقوال" and "خطوةً بخطوة". This is in line with the terminology of paraphrasing (Newmark, 1991, pp.168-74)

Idioms

Table 6

No.	English idiom	Literal translation	Arabic equivalents
1	There were no signs of substantial strain in The cornerstone of PDRY's foreign policy. (p.37).	لم تكن هناك علامات على وجود توتر كبير في حجر الزاوية للسياسة الخارجية لجمهورية اليمن الديمقراطية الشعبية.	لم تكن هناك علامات على وجود توتر كبير في الركيزة الأساسية للسياسة الخارجية لجمهورية اليمن الديمقراطية الشعبية. (ص 94).
2	While relations with China never reaching breaking point . (p. 38).	إلا أن العلاقات مع الصين لم تصل البتة إلى نقطة الانكسار.	إلا أن العلاقات مع الصين لم تصل البتة إلى مرحلة الانهيار. (ص 94).

3	Aden was to play host to president Ali Khamene. (p. 38).	كانت عدن على وشك لعب استضافة للرئيس علي خامنئي.	كانت عدن على وشك استضافة الرئيس علي خامنئي. (ص 95).
4	There were reports of troops being placed on alert . (p. 39).	كانت هناك أنباء عن وحدات عسكرية وُضعت على يقظة.	كانت هناك أنباء عن وحدات عسكرية وُضعت على أهبة الاستعداد. (ص 97).

As has been shown above, the literal translation for such idiomatic expressions will surely result in distorting the intended meaning of the ST and affecting the rhetorical and aesthetic aspects of the TT. For example, the literal translation for the idiomatic expression *cornerstone* in the extract "the **cornerstone** of the PDRY foreign policy" is **حجر الزاوية**. It is worth noting that adopting such a translation does not reflect the intended meaning of the ST idiom more effectively and may result in the lack of the aesthetic and rhetoric depth of the TT that is in many times required.

Regarding the adequacy of the TL equivalent **حجر الأساس** as a counterpart to the ST idiomatic expression in this context is, however, inaccessible, and inadequate to leave on the TT readership the same effect left on the readership of the ST, as it normally and culturally used as a symbol for laying the first stone of any project, and which is, however, far away from the soul of the original's meaning. Thereupon, faraway from literal translation and avoiding to consult the TL equivalent as well, an attempt had been made to create a kind of proximity between the ST and the TT regarding meaning. Therefore, in rendering the idiomatic expression *cornerstone*, the translator took into account the micro and macro dimensions of the text relying on the context and the total meaning of the ST message which hints, in such a context, at the fundamental pillar of the foreign policy of PDRY. Thereupon, he has rendered the idiomatic expression *cornerstone* into "الركيزة الأساسية للسياسة الخارجية" in the TT. In this sense, it has been felt that the intended meaning of the ST was effectively reflected and the translator was allowed to create a kind of adequacy between the two messages. In this regard, it is worth noting that the translator paid attention to the acceptability and readability of the TT at the expense of accuracy of the ST. Hence, cultural equivalent procedure was used.

Another interesting example is "while relations with China never reaching **breaking point**". Its literal translation is "إلا أن العلاقات مع الصين لم تصل البتة إلى درجة الانكسار". It seems that literal translation is to some extent acceptable, and the possibility of catching the sense of this expression is available as its general meaning, in such a context, is beating about the collapse of relation between south Yemen and China. Particularly, in the late seventies the relation between south Yemen and China was getting worse and worse, yet it never reached the degree of complete collapse. Moreover, taking into account that there is no fully equivalent even between the components of the same language (cf. Jakobson, 1959, p.139), the possibility of nearly close equivalent in the TL is available, that is, the idiomatic phrase **مرحلة حرجة** lit. "critical point" which can be used as an equivalent to the ST idiom *breaking point* **إلا أن العلاقات لم تصل إلى مرحلة حرجة**. However, the translator here, for the sake of reproducing the most accurate and faithful image of the ST, paraphrased the ST idiomatic phrase **breaking point** into Arabic as **مرحلة الانهيار التام** which is nearly close to the meaning of the ST, to be as an equivalent in the TL to the idiomatic expression "breaking point" in the ST. Therein, the final translation will be:

إلا أن العلاقات مع الصين لم تصل البتة إلى مرحلة الانهيار التام.

One more example is the idiomatic expression *play host* in the extract "Aden was about to play host to president Ali Khamenei" which literally means "كانت عدن على وشك لعب استضافة للرئيس علي خامنئي". Taking into account the idea that idioms have both (cf. Baker, 1992, p.66), literal meaning (denotative meaning) which is, in some cases, misleading and adopting it in the TL does violate the intended meaning of the ST, and surely strike the TT receptor, and idiomatic meaning (connotative meaning) which is to a considerable extent recognized by relying on the collocational environment that surrounds the idiom. Consequently, in rendering the ST idiom, the translator, with the absence of equivalent in the TL and the failure of literal translation to decode it as well, relied on the context to decode the meaning of this idiom. Meanwhile, he, in an attempt to maintain a desired level of naturalness, opted for reducing the structure of the ST idiom *play host* lit. "يلعب استضافة", that is, he has deleted the lexical item *play*, as deleting it does not harm the author's intentions or alter the text type focus but, on the contrary, retaining it in the TT will definitively complicate the matter of understanding the intended meaning of the ST message, and then translated the word *host* literally to "استضافة". So, the final translation will be: "كانت عدن على وشك استضافة الرئيس علي خامنئي". This is in line with Malone's (1988) terminology (Reduction).

The last example is "There were reports of troops being **placed on alert**." The core meaning of this example is that the military troops were put in readiness. Translating this phrase requires understanding the idiom and finding its natural equivalent in Arabic, especially within a military context. Arabic has specific, well-established and professional phrases for this concept such as **في حالة** or **على أهبة الاستعداد** or **استنفار**. These two translations prioritize meaning and make the expression seem natural in Arabic. The suitable translation procedure used is cultural substitution (Vinay and Darbeint, 1995), or functional equivalent (Newmark, 1988), since both idioms in English and its Arabic equivalent are suitable to express military readiness or preparedness, and this procedure involves replacing a culture-specific idiom in the SL (English) with an idiom in the TL (Arabic), that has the same meaning, impact, and connotation, and makes the translation read like an original text, not a translation.

Conclusion

This study identified six primary lexical categories encountered during the translation process of the book *Revolution and Foreign Policy: The Case of South Yemen (1967-1987)*. They are: proper nouns, metaphors, similes, polysemy, collocations and idioms. To address lexical challenges, particularly in the context of a historical informative source text, many translation procedures were used in order to help the target language readers to understand the source text intent. In translating proper nouns three procedures were used: transference, naturalization and translation; in nouns consisting of two or three names, two integrated procedures can be used, for examples: transference + naturalization, naturalization + translation, or vice versa, transference + translation). Three procedures were used in translating metaphors: reproducing the same image in the TL, converting metaphor into sense, replacing the image in the SL with a standard image in the TL. In translating similes three procedures were used: translating simile by simile plus sense, omission and literal translation. In translating polysemouse words, context of these words helped the translator/researcher to choose the proper Arabic equivalents, therefore, transposition and omission were carefully used. In translating collocations five procedures were used: literal translation, transposition, functional equivalent, couplets

(transposition + expansion) and modulation. In translation idioms three procedures were used: paraphrase, functional equivalent and omission. Overall, this study underscores the multifaceted and complex nature of the translation process. Achieving an accurate and coherent target text necessitates a nuanced understanding of various linguistic and cultural factors, demanding careful consideration and strategic application of appropriate translation procedures.

The researcher recommend that during the process of translation translators, translation students should pay attention to all translation problems that lead to misunderstanding of source texts, and hence lead to mistranslation. Moreover, cultural information should be taken into account during translation process. It is also recommended that theorists' translation procedures should be known well by both translation students and translators in order to use the suitable procedure for each translation problem.

References

- Alabbasi, A. (2012). *Introduction to translation: A theoretical and practical course book*. (3rd ed.) Dar Al-kutub.
- Almanna, A. (2016). *The Routledge course in translation annotation: Arabic-English-Arabic*. New York. Routledge.
- Baker, M. (1992). *In other words: A coursebook on translation*. Routledge.
- Baker, M. (2011). *In other words: A coursebook on translation* (2nd ed.). Routledge.
- Brinton, L. and Akimoto, M. (Eds.). (1999). *Collocational and idiomatic aspects of composite predicates in the history of English*. Amsterdam: Jhon Benjammines.
- Bussman, H. (Ed. and trans.). (1996). *Routledge dictionary of language and linguistics*. London: Routledge.
- Catford, J. (1965). *A linguistic theory of translation*. London: Oxford University Press.
- Catford, J. C. (1974). *A linguistic theory of translation*. London: Oxford University Press.
- Creswell, J. (2007). *Qualitative inquiry and research design: Choosing among five approaches*. Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage.
- Crystal, D. (1980). *A dictionary of linguistics and phonetics*. Blackwell.
- Dale, R., et al. (2000). (eds.). *Handbook of natural language processing*. New York: Marcel Dekker: Inc.
- Geeraerts, D. (2010). *Theories of lexical semantics* (1st ed.). New York, NY: Oxford University Press.
- Ghazala, H. (2008). *Translation as problems and solutions: A textbook for university students and trainee translators*. (3rd ed.). Beirut: Dar El-Ilm Limalayin.
- Ghazala, H. (2021). *A textbook of legal translation: Problems and solutions*. Makkah Al-Mukarramah: Konooz Al-Marifa.
- Halliday, F. (1970). *Revolution and foreign policy: The case of south Yemen 1967-1987*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Jakobson, R. (1959). On linguistic aspects of translation. In R.A. Brower (ed). *On translation*, (1959), pp. 232-239. Cambridge, MA: Harvard University Press.

Larson, M. L. (1984). *Meaning-based translation: A guide to cross-language equivalence*. University Press of America.

Longman Dictionary of Contemporary English (app.2009)

McCawley, J. (1968). The role of semantics in a grammar. In E. Bach & R. Harms (eds.), *Universals in linguistic theory*, pp. 125- 170. New York: Holt, Rinehart, and Winston.

Merriam Webster dictionary (app. 2021)

Munday, J. (2008). *Introducing translation studies: Theories and applications*. (2nd Ed.). Taylor & Francis e- Library. Routledge.

Newmark, P. (1988). *A textbook of translation*. London/New York: Prentice Hall.

Newmark, P. (2001). *Approaches to translation*. Oxford: Pergamon.

Nida, E. (1964). *Toward a science of translating*. Shanghai: Shanghai Foreign Language Education Press.

Nida, E., & Taber, C. (1969). *The theory and practice of translation*. Leiden: E. J. Brill.

Nunan, D. (2000). Toward a collaborative approach to curriculum development: A case study. *TESOL Quarterly*, 23(1), 9. doi:10.2307/3587505

Palmer, F. R. (1981). *Semantics: A new outline* (2nd ed.). Cambridge, UK: Cambridge University Press. (Original work published 1976)

Richard, J., & Schmidt, R. (2010). *Longman dictionary of language teaching and applied linguistics*. (4th ed.). London: Pearson Education Limited.

Sadiq, S. (2008). Some semantic, stylistic and cultural problems of translation with special reference to translating the glorious Qur'ân. *Sayyab Translation Journal*, 1,37-59.

Sandelowski, M., & Barroso, J. (2007). *Handbook for synthesizing qualitative research*. New York: Springer.

Tavakoli, H. (2012). *A dictionary of research methodology and statistics in applied linguistics*. Tehran: Rahnama Press.

Venuti, L. (1995). *The translator's invisibility: A history of translation*. London and New York: Routledge

Vinay, J. P., & Darbelnet, J. (1995). *Comparative stylistics of French and English: A methodology for translation*. John Benjamins Publishing Company.